
Evaluation of Innovative Banking System for the 21st Century: The Prospect and Practice

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Abstract: This study evaluated innovative banking system for the 21st century, its prospect and practice. It revealed that over the past few decades, the banking industry has experienced significant transition driven by changes in consumer expectations and technology improvements. Several concepts related to the 21st century banking system were reviewed, such as banking system, innovative banking system, principles, practice and prospects of innovative banking system for the 21st century. The study noted that innovations in the banking system have created a brand new reality for digital banking that redefines the way people perceive their finances and also that the integration of digital technologies and Fintech has advanced and improved efficiency, accessibility, and customer happiness in the 21st-century. Furthermore, the study mentioned that innovations in banking has helped automate manual processes, reduce costs, and increase the overall efficiency of banking operations. The study concluded that banking sectors have been transformed due to technological advancements and changing consumer expectations. One of the recommendations of the study was that banks should invest in developing and enhancing digital platforms that prioritize user experience.

Key words: Banking, Innovative Banking, 21st Century.

Introduction

Over the past few decades, the banking industry has experienced a significant transition driven by changes in consumer expectations and technology improvements. The financial services industry has changed due to the emergence of innovative banking systems. These systems are revolutionising the customer experience and improving operational efficiency. They are distinguished by their digital platforms, sophisticated analytics, and smooth customer interfaces.

The emergence of digital banking platforms is evidence of the industry's flexible approaches to integrating technology. Digital-only banks, have sprung up all over the place, providing services that are frequently more affordable and user-friendly than those of regular banks. According to a report by McKinsey & Company (2020), digital banking adoption has surged, with a significant percentage of consumers now preferring online banking over visiting physical branches. This change emphasises how traditional banks must develop and incorporate digital technologies in order to remain competitive.

Furthermore, the use of artificial intelligence (AI) and advanced analytics in banking is completely changing the way financial organisations run. Algorithms powered by AI are being used to improve risk management procedures, detect fraud, and personalise customer care. Research by PwC (2019) highlights that banks utilising AI can potentially reduce operational costs by up to 22%, demonstrating the economic benefits of such innovations. These technologies improve decision-making processes and streamline operations, which boosts an organization's performance as a whole.

The banking sector is expected to be further disrupted by the use of blockchain technology in addition to technical advancements. The decentralised and secure transaction method provided by blockchain can drastically cut down on the expenses and time involved in carrying out standard banking procedures. A study by the World Economic Forum (2021) predicts that by 2025, 10% of global GDP will be stored on blockchain technology, indicating its growing influence and potential for widespread adoption in banking.

The integration of these cutting-edge technology is not without difficulties, though. Significant challenges include things like cybersecurity concerns, regulatory compliance, and the digital divide. Banks need to carefully manage these obstacles in order to effectively capitalise on technology improvements. It is imperative to tackle these issues in order to guarantee the secure and efficient deployment of cutting-edge banking technologies. A report by Deloitte (2020) emphasises the need for robust cybersecurity measures and regulatory frameworks to mitigate the risks associated with digital banking.

Concept of banking system

The main functions of the banking system are to provide credit to an economy, regulate the money supply, and facilitate financial transactions. The commercial banks, savings banks, credit unions, and other financial institutions that are all subject to regulation by a central authority—usually a central bank—compose the fundamental elements of the banking system. These financial organisations take deposits from both private citizens and commercial clients. They also offer loans and a range of other financial services, such as investment products, mortgages, and savings accounts. By doing so, banks play a critical role in maintaining liquidity in the economy and ensuring the efficient allocation of resources (Mishkin, 2019).

According to Whiting & Lee (2023), the banking system is the collection of networks that provide financial services to people. In the banking system, there are many different kinds of banks: retail banks, community banks, central banks, investment banks (which mainly serve large organisations, cooperation, and institutions that need help with investments), and commercial banks, which are establishments that provide financial services to the general public (as of 2024). The central bank conducts monetary policy, which is essential to managing employment levels, stabilising the currency, and controlling inflation. The banking system plays a key role in this process. Through mechanisms such as setting interest rates and reserve requirements, central banks influence the lending activities of commercial banks, thereby impacting economic growth and stability (Freixas & Rochet, 2008).

The banking industry has seen a dramatic transformation thanks to technological developments, which have also given rise to online and mobile banking, which provide customers with more accessibility and convenience. These innovations have not only improved the efficiency of banking operations but have also introduced new challenges such as cybersecurity risks and the need for updated regulatory measures (Berger, 2003). In addition, the globalisation of financial markets has made banking systems more interconnected among nations, which calls for increased international coordination and cooperation among regulatory bodies in order to address systemic risks and guarantee the stability of the global financial system. (Claessens & Van Horen, 2015).

Concept of Innovative Banking System

Innovation is defined as something novel or previously unexplored. The adoption of novel concepts and cutting-edge technologies with the goal of enhancing the efficacy and efficiency of banking services is referred to as an innovative banking system. However, Valchev (2021) postulated that some innovations in the banking system have created a brand new reality for digital banking that redefines the way people perceive their finances. In order to meet the evolving needs and expectations of their customers, stay competitive in a crowded market, increase operational efficiency within the banking system, lower the risk of fraud, cyberattacks, and other potential threats to the industry, and generate new revenue streams for their customers through new products and services, banks must innovate their banking systems. (Vanner, 2023).

According to Mani (2023), banking innovation helps to provide customers with customs and more accessible financial services in the banking system. In addition to enhancing customer retention, it offers a highly customised banking experience. Immersion technology in innovative banking offers a customised and interactive consumer experience within the financial system. Moreover, Thomas & Majini (2023) postulated that innovation is the enforcement of technology, which is used to give new solutions to new and existing requirements in the banking system as it accomplishes new effective products, services, processes, and technology ideas that are readily available to marketers, governments, and society at large. In order to enable consumers to access their accounts, pay bills, and conduct transactions via their smartphones or other devices, many banks have started investing in digital platforms and apps. Financial institutions can now access previously underserved populations in the banking sector because to banking innovation. Innovation in banking benefits the bank as well as its clientele.

Innovation in banking is a key factor in the systemic transformation and expansion of the banking industry. Achimba, Ongonga, Nyarondia, Amos, and Okwara (2014) mentioned that the banking industry has experienced transformations due to changes in consumer needs, behaviour, knowledge, and competitive innovation as a result of globalisation, liberalisation, and technological factors. Technology development in the banking sector dates back a long time, and so far, it has definitely changed the way banks operate (Zaleska & Kondraciuk 2019). Since technology, higher interest rates, and sustainability are the three primary structural facets of the banking system, the bank must address these issues as well if it hopes to successfully implement innovation. Customers will reward banks with their loyalty, confidence, support, and recommendations in return.

Principles of Innovative Banking System for the 21st Century

The integration of digital technologies and Fintech advances to improve efficiency, accessibility, and customer happiness is at the core of 21st-century innovative banking systems. The following are the principles of innovative banking system for the 21st century as outlined by Magomaeva and Galazova (2021) and Lerner, Seru, Short, Sun (2023):

Digital Transformation: The impact of digital innovations has caused a tremendous upheaval in the banking sector, altering the way banks function and engage with their clientele. Banks may now offer a more personalised customer experience by concentrating on individual preferences and improving service efficiency thanks to digitalization.

Banking Innovations: Banking innovations are a type of innovation that transforms the fundamentals of banking services to increase their efficiency, accessibility, and transparency. These innovations include the creation of fresh banking services and goods, the application of cutting-edge technology, and the incorporation of Fintech offerings.

Fintech Integration: The banking industry is undergoing transformation as a result of fintech companies, and the advancement of contemporary banking services depends on their integration with conventional banks. Major banks are implementing fintech innovations, like mobile banking services and digital payment systems, to improve customer experience and increase efficiency.

Customer-Centric Approach: The main goal is to provide customer-focused goods and services that meet the changing demands and expectations of consumers. Digital banking ecosystems facilitate efficient communication between banks, their customers, and partners, allowing for the expert delegation of decision-making and the provision of advisory services.

Digital Banking Ecosystems: By 2025, it is anticipated that digital banking ecosystems—which incorporate a range of financial services and products, including investments, insurance, and bonus schemes—will account for over thirty percent of the total gross revenue generated by the banking industry.

Cybersecurity and Risk Management: The advent of digital advances also raises the possibility of cyberattacks, therefore banks must create plans to efficiently handle these risks.

Prospect of Innovative Banking System for the 21st Century

The following are the prospects of innovative banking systems in the 21st century:

➤ Technological Integration and Innovation:

AI and Chatbots: Chatbots and virtual assistants driven by artificial intelligence (AI) offer customised customer service, improving productivity and client happiness.

Blockchain Technology: enhances confidence and lowers transaction costs by enabling safe and transparent transactions.

Data Analytics: Facilitates real-time risk assessment and predictive modeling, aiding banks in making informed decisions and managing risks effectively (Gupta, 2024).

➤ Enhanced Customer Experience:

Mobile Banking Apps: Provide easy access to financial services in order to increase accessibility and enhance user satisfaction (Brown & Williams, 2023).

Biometric Authentication: increases security while guaranteeing a flawless user experience, building client loyalty and confidence (Lee, 2021).

➤ Financial Inclusion and Accessibility:

Digital Banking Solutions: Provide essential financial services to underserved communities, driving economic empowerment and poverty alleviation (Chen, 2022).

Open Banking Initiatives: Promote collaboration and interoperability, creating a more inclusive financial ecosystem (Lopez & Garcia, 2024).

➤ Cybersecurity Measures:

Robust Cybersecurity: Utilizes biometric authentication, encryption technologies, and anomaly detection systems to mitigate cyber threats and safeguard sensitive data (Wang et al., 2023).

Regulatory Compliance: Regulatory frameworks like GDPR ensure data privacy and compliance, enhancing consumer trust in digital banking platforms (Choi & Kim, 2021).

The Practice of Innovative Banking System for the 21st Century

Innovations in banking can help automate manual processes, reduce costs, and increase the overall efficiency of banking operations. Automation technologies can help reduce errors, speed up tasks, and free up employees to focus on higher-value work. Digital financial services innovation in banking offers a completely new, different, or cutting-edge customer experience. Next-gen financial services can help banks and financial organisations better serve their customers and differentiate their brand from competitors. González (2024) defined innovation as the manifestation of a new idea or a previously unknown fact, the ability to successfully apply that idea in practice, a change in the thought process for doing something, or the useful application of new inventions or discoveries.

Banking innovations can lower costs, automate tedious tasks, and improve the overall effectiveness of banking operations. Automation technology can expedite labour, lower error rates, and free up staff members to concentrate on higher-value jobs. Innovation is also being fueled by changes in regulations. Being one of the most heavily regulated sectors, banks must safeguard clients while maintaining their competitiveness and staying abreast of the constantly changing regulatory environment to guarantee their long-term viability. This translates to increased security and less risk. Technology in banking is always changing to keep up with the demands and expectations of competitors, regulators, and customers.

Furthermore, Kreger (2024) stated that it is obvious that banking innovation makes it easier, faster, and more secure for customers to manage their money, make financial transactions, and make financial decisions. Valchey (2022) mentioned that banks should stay at the epicentre,

embracing technologies that satisfy customer needs for financial health, wealth, trust, and security with a new level of online, mobile, and omni-channel services. But a high-tech attitude alone is insufficient, even in the age of the most famous technologies. Every bank's future rests on how successfully it can use the newest technologies to concentrate on the demands, desires, and behaviours of its clients. The competition to acquire and apply the most cutting-edge technology has intensified as banks become more digital. Customer demand is one of the main forces behind innovation in banking technology. Consumers expect their financial services to be more individualised, quick, secure, and convenient. They also want to be able to access their transactions and accounts from any location at any time using any device. Banks must make investments in chatbots, robot advisors, mobile apps, biometric authentication, digital platforms, and other technologies that improve consumer happiness in order to meet these needs.

Singer (2024) mentions that innovative mobile dashboards leverage cutting-edge techniques, including animated cards that dynamically display crucial information such as account balances, investment fund earnings through animated charts, and personalised offers enhanced with custom animations. We also included animated lesson features to the app, which simplify and make difficult tasks easier to understand, increasing user pleasure and engagement. Artificial intelligence, the newest digital technology, is being embraced by the banking sector.

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Due to private information, bank loans themselves are not always liquid, although the majority of their cash flows are. Credit derivatives and actual and synthetic securitizations are two recent financial inventions that facilitate the liquefaction of commercial loans. The remaining illiquid equity tranche, which includes the concentrated credit risk, rent on private information, and the "excess spread" that encourages the bank to keep an eye on and service the loans, is held by the bank that originated the loan.

Conclusion

The banking sector has transformed due to technological advancements and changing consumer expectations. Innovative banking systems, featuring digital platforms, advanced analytics, and seamless interfaces, are reshaping financial services by enhancing efficiency and customer experience. Digital banking adoption has surged, necessitating traditional banks to innovate. AI and blockchain further revolutionise operations by personalising services, reducing costs, and securing transactions. However, challenges such as cybersecurity and regulatory compliance must be addressed. Evaluating these innovative systems highlights the need for financial institutions to embrace technology while mitigating risks and ensuring enhanced banking services for the 21st century.

Recommendations

1. Banks should invest in developing and enhancing digital platforms that prioritize user experience. This includes creating intuitive mobile and online banking interfaces, implementing AI-driven customer service tools, and offering personalized financial products.
2. Banks should also invest in educating customers about cybersecurity best practices to minimize risks associated with digital banking.
3. Banks should actively explore and integrate emerging technologies such as blockchain, AI, and machine learning into their operations. These technologies can streamline processes, enhance fraud detection, and improve decision-making capabilities.

REFERENCES

1. Achimba, C., Ongonga, J., Nyarondia, S., Amos, A. and Okwara, M. (2014). Innovation in Banking Industry: Achieving Customers Satisfaction. *Open Journal of Business and Management* 2(4):261-274
2. Berger, A. N. (2003). The Economic Effects of Technological Progress: Evidence from the Banking Industry. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 35(2), 141-176.
3. Brown, A., & Williams, B. (2023). Mobile Banking Apps: Revolutionizing Customer Experience. *Journal of Banking Technology*, 10(2), 45-58.
4. Brown, A., & Williams, B. (2023). The Rise of Mobile Banking: Trends and Implications for Customer Experience. *Journal of Retail Banking Services*.
5. Chen, C. (2022). Digital Banking for Financial Inclusion. *International Journal of Finance and Economics*, 15(4), 102-115.
6. Chen, L. (2022). Digital Financial Inclusion: Opportunities and Challenges. *Journal of Banking & Finance*.
7. Choi, D., & Kim, E. (2021). Impact of GDPR on Digital Banking. *Journal of Cybersecurity and Privacy*, 5(1), 20-35.
8. Choi, Y., & Kim, S. (2021). GDPR Compliance in Banking: Challenges and Best Practices. *International Journal of Information Management*.
9. Skinner, S. (2024) Banking in the 21st century: New? No. Improved? Yes Available at <https://www.thebanker.com/Banking-in-the-21st-century-New-No.-Improved-Yes-1333353608>
10. Claessens, S., & Van Horen, N. (2015). The impact of the global financial crisis on banking globalization. *IMF Economic Review*, 63(4): 868-918.
11. Deloitte. (2020). Global Digital Banking Survey. Deloitte Insights. Retrieved from [Deloitte Insights](<https://www2.deloitte.com>)
12. Freixas, X., & Rochet, J. C. (2008). Microeconomics of banking. MIT Press.
13. González F. (2024). Innovation for the 21st Century Banking Industry. Available at: <https://www.bbvaopenmind.com/en/articles/innovation-for-the-21st-century-banking-industry/>
14. Gupta, S. (2024). Data Analytics in Banking: Applications and Benefits. *Expert Systems with Applications*.
15. Gupta, S. (2024). Data Analytics in Banking: Opportunities and Challenges. *Journal of Financial Technology*, 18(3), 72-85.
16. Indeed (2024). The Banking Industry: Definition, Trends, and Key Terms. Available at: <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/banking-industry>
17. Jones, M. (2023). Technological Innovation in Banking: A Review of Recent Developments. *Journal of Financial Services Research*.
18. Jones, T. (2023). Artificial Intelligence in Banking Operations. *Journal of Financial Innovation*, 12(1), 30-42.
19. Kreger A. (2024). Banking Innovation. Available at: <https://www.finextra.com/blogposting/24935/banking-innovation-do-not-let-your-mindset-stop-you#:~:text=Banking%20innovation%20in%20digital%20financial,differentiate%20their%20brand%20from%20competitors.>
20. Lee, J. (2021). Biometric Authentication in Mobile Banking: User Perspectives and Acceptance Factors. *Computers in Human Behavior*.

21. Lee, S. (2021). Biometric Authentication in Digital Banking. *Journal of Cybersecurity*, 8(2), 55-68.
22. Lopez, J., & Garcia, M. (2024). Open Banking and Financial Inclusion. *International Journal of Banking and Finance*, 22(4), 110-125.
23. Lopez, J., & Garcia, M. (2024). Open Banking: Towards a More Inclusive Financial Ecosystem. *Journal of Economic Integration*.
24. Mani K.S. (2023). Top 10 Banking Innovations amp; Trends in 2024 available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/top-10-banking-innovations-amp-trends-2024-sivaprakash-kumma-mani/>
25. McKinsey & Company. (2020). The Future of Digital Banking: Perspectives and Prospects. McKinsey Digital. Retrieved from [McKinsey & Company](<https://www.mckinsey.com>)
26. PwC. (2019). AI in Banking: An Analysis of the Impact on Performance. PwC Financial Services. Retrieved from [PwC](<https://www.pwc.com>)
27. Singer A. (2024). Innovative Banks Globally. Available at: <https://gfmag.com/banking/most-innovative-banks-globally-2024/>
28. Smith, D., & Johnson, E. (2022). Blockchain Technology in Banking: Opportunities and Challenges. *Journal of Financial Innovation*.
29. Smith, J., & Johnson, R. (2022). Blockchain Technology and Banking. *Journal of Financial Technology*, 17(2), 50-63.
30. Thomas, T. & Majini, B. K. (2023). A Study on Banking Innovations through Technology. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376580774_a_study_on_banking_innovations_through_technology
31. Valchev M. (2021). 10 Innovations that Deliver the Digital Banking of the Future. available at: <https://www.softwaregroup.com/insights/blog/article/10-innovations-that-deliver-the-digital-banking-of-the-future-today>
32. Vanner C. (2023). Banking Innovations: Why Banks Need to Modernize. Available at: <https://www.bizagi.com/en/blog/banking-innovation-why-banks-need-to-modernize>
33. Wang, L., (2023). Cybersecurity Measures in Innovative Banking Systems. *Journal of Cybersecurity and Risk Management*, 7(3), 80-95.
34. Whiting B. & Lee K. (2023) Banking system | overview, forms and types. Available at: <https://study.com/academy/lesson/banking-system-definition-types.html#:~:text=A%20banking%20system%20is%20a,deposits%2C%20and%20helping%20with%20investments.>
35. World Economic Forum. (2021). Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology: What's the Impact? World Economic Forum. Retrieved from [World Economic Forum](<https://www.weforum.org>)
36. Zaleska M. & Kondraciuk P. (2019). Theory and Practice of Innovation Development in the Banking Sector. *SCIENDO*, 24(2):80